

Managing human resource development of educators in inclusion-based elementary school

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ABSTRACT

This study was a descriptive qualitative research. The respondents of were headmasters, human resource (HR) coordinators, teachers and special guide teachers. Data were collected through observation, interview, and documentation. Data were validated using source and method triangulations. Data were then analyzed. The results are as follows: 1) HR planning started from needs preparation, recruitment, selection, placement, orientation and adaptation to the new workplaces. The difference is found in SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto compared to the other two elementary schools. The recruitment of its new employees at all levels is carried out by the Committee of Education and Teaching from recruitment to orientation stages; 2) HR development is basically the same, i.e. through education or training. The difference is also found in SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto, where it provides scholarships; 3) HR evaluation is implemented by the headmasters regularly every semester in the form of classroom supervision and administration; 4) Compensation and other benefits received by employees depend on the employees' work term, types of employees (job training employees, non-permanent employees, permanent employees, and school headmasters).

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1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of the Indonesian country was formed is to educate the life of a nation and it is contained in the opening of the UUD 1945. The realization of it can be done through education. Education is one place to increase human resources for the achievement of national development. As a determinant of success, improving the quality of human resources is carried out through educational programs based on global developments and advances in science and technology and also based on faith and devotion.

Education is a human right where education is open, non-discriminatory, and reaches all citizens without exception. Education lasts a last time and can be done anytime and anywhere as long as humans can do it. Education is realized through various formal, informal, and non-formal education activities. Formal education activities consist of basic education, secondary education, and higher education.

Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning National Education System chapter IV article 5 [1] states that "every citizen has the same right to obtain a quality education and for citizens who have physical, emotional, mental, intellectual and/or social disabilities are entitled to special education". As a consequence of the regulation, the government through the Ministry of National Education established an educational concept

that does not discriminate against the background of children's lives due to physical or mental disability through special education and special service education. This is implemented through Minister of National Education Regulation No. 70 of 2009 [2] concerning inclusive education for students who have disabilities and have the potential for intelligence and/or special talents, is by providing opportunities for students with special needs to attend education in regular schools (elementary, junior high, high school / vocational school) in the surrounding environment.

According to Ilahi [3], inclusive education is defined as "a concept that accommodates all children with special needs or children who have difficulty reading and writing". The existence of inclusive schools is expected to provide maximum opportunities for the child with special needs to study in regular schools designated as inclusive schools so that the child with special needs can socialize well and be more accepted by the community.

The components that must exist and greatly affect the success of an educational institution are students and teachers. Students are learning subjects in the form of raw materials and later will be formed through a process with a variety of support resources. The teacher is an instrumental input that directly influences the success of education and the resulting student output is primarily the role of the teacher which is one of the resources whose task is to provide lessons to the subject. Therefore, for schools to recruit qualified human resources, it requires a system of recruiting educators. According to Arikunto and Yuliana [4], the teacher management process consists of planning in which there is a needs analysis, determining teacher recruitment requirements, job vacancy announcements, teacher selection, acceptance announcements, and also placement and assignments as for the process, the teacher maintenance with compensation, benefits, and health insurance so that later teachers can become professional teachers as expected by school institutions.

Sutrisno [5] explains that "human resources are defined as sources of strength that come from humans who can be utilized by the organization". Furthermore, Arifin [6] explains that human resources must always be oriented to the vision, mission, goals and objectives of the organization. To achieve this vision, mission and goals, humans need to have character and competency values. Arifin [6] explains that "there are five character values and competencies that must be possessed, namely motivation, attitudes or innate traits, self-concept, knowledge and skills". Teachers as the spearhead of quality education service providers in inclusive education need to be improved. The government should make sure the availability of competent resources in designated inclusive education units. So far, efforts to improve teacher understanding and knowledge about inclusive education have often been carried out in the form of training. However, the increasing of the inclusive competence school teachers by district/city governments has not produce maximum results. These gaps or differences and disparities between expectations and reality are commonly identified as strategic problems that need to be resolved through targeted development programs following their fields of work. Quality management of educators' human resources is expected to optimize their potential to be able to support the formation of quality education. In this case, human resources educators become the spearhead in solving problems faced by education.

Nandini and Taj [7] explained that inclusive education requires teacher preparation according to their needs. This needs to require teachers who are skilled and motivated and quite competent to deal with complexity in the classroom. In-service training for inclusive education teachers is successful if it is carefully programmed in terms of time, funds, target groups, resources so that in training it can create inclusive education modules that are integrated into the teaching and learning process. Thus the preparation of the implementation of inclusive education is not only the duty of the school but also the responsibility of the government both local and central government. The same thing was expressed by Okongo, *et al.* [8] with the results explained that inadequate resources can influence the implementation of inclusive education. Therefore, adequate teaching and learning resources must be provided to ensure effective education implementation and more funding for the provision of teaching materials for the needs of teachers in inclusive schools.

School is an organization of educational institutions in which there are various resources involved so that an organization runs smoothly. The resources intended are, environmental resources and human resources, in this case however the completeness of environmental resources, and infrastructure fulfilled, but if the human resources that run the school program are less competent in their duties, it will be difficult to achieve the expected goals. This proves that the role of the teacher is very important in a school, especially related to the latest education programs currently regarding the existence of inclusive school programs implemented in various countries. Research conducted by Jelas [9] revealed that with the new paradigm in education programs in Malaysia that implemented an inclusive program, teachers were prepared to develop their abilities related to roles as facilitators of inclusive teachers. Related to this, so that schools can utilize their human resources also requires education and training to support the effectiveness of achieving school goals.

Being a professional teacher requires several requirements that must be fulfilled. Fulfillment of these requirements is none other for future teacher candidates, so they can fulfill their duties to improve the quality of education through assignments as professional instructors and educators. One way is through various kinds of training programs. This was conveyed by Csorba [10] that to increase teacher access and participation in basic education for continuous training based on digital resources and mixed learning courses, to support key young school children need to prepare training needs analysis, identify priority areas of interest, training planning solutions, designing training events and resources, accrediting programs, deliver programs, integrate new information and communication technologies, manage training activities, assess the skills of the trainees and develop creative anticipatory action strategies, to create a sustainable environment education in basic education and culture that encourages and values vocational learning and development.

Increased professionalism was realized through a systematic and integrated process in the form of management of teaching and education staff, starting from the planning process to the evaluation and dismissal procedures. Management of educational personnel aims to empower the teaching staff effectively and efficiently to achieve optimal results, but still in pleasant conditions to realize uniformity of treatment and legal certainty for elementary school education personnel in carrying out their duties and functions, authorities, and responsibilities under applicable laws and regulations. Teachers are human resources in schools. Human resources greatly contribute to improving organizational performance (schools) and have an impact on improving the quality of education. This was also conveyed in Hamid, *et al.* [11] research with the result that human resources were an important source of competitive advantage. Strategic human resource management has an impact on organizational performance, the conclusion is the way an organization manages its human resources has a significant relationship with organizational performance. Human resource system can contribute to a sustainable competitive advantage through facilitating competency development and creation of good relationships

Being a teacher is not only an instructor, but also serves as an educator and is responsible for helping students develop into a whole human being and be useful for the environment. Nowadays where education is influenced by globalization requires teachers to develop their critical attitude so that they can make wise decisions. With the overflow of information, whether it is positive and negative, the teacher as an educator in the school is tasked with helping students to see problems from various sides, not just one side. That way, the teacher will teach students to think rationally, critically, creatively, and innovatively. The quality of education is a problem that influenced by various factors. One of the biggest contributing factors is education human resources. Human resources in the world of education are important and serious things to be considered by all stakeholders. The quality of education will achieve the best improvement if the quality of teaching staff is increased. A school institution will be seen as successful not from the institution itself but by looking from the support of its resources, especially its human resources that is the teaching staff. Based on this explanation, it is necessary to have an in-depth study in terms of the management of educator resources related to the planning of educators, the development of educators, the assessment of educators, and the compensation system.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This study was a descriptive qualitative research. It was conducted from May to September 2018 in SDIT Annida Sokaraja, SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto and SD Terpadu Putra Harapan in Purwokerto, Central Java, Indonesia. The respondents were headmasters, HR coordinators, teachers and special guide teachers. Data were collected through observation, interview, and documentation. Data were validated using source and method triangulations. Table 1 presents the data collection instruments and techniques, while Figure 1 explains the implementation stage in analyzing research data.

Figure 1. Interactive model data analysis according to Miles and Huberman [12]

Table 1. Data collection instruments and techniques.

No	Aspect	Data source	Data collecting technique
1	HR Planning	1. Recruitment	a. Interview
		2. Selection and placement process	b. Documentation
		3. Selection and placement result	
		4. HR planning effectiveness	
2	HR Development	1. Forms of HR training and development	a. Interview
		2. Effectiveness of HR training and development	b. Documentation
3	HR Performance Assessment	1. Standardize performance assessment	a. Interview
		2. Performance assessment	b. Observation
		3. Form of performance assessment	c. Documentation
4	Compensation and HR welfare policies	1. Compensation and HR welfare administration	a. Interview
		2. Effectiveness of compensation and HR welfare administration	b. Documentation

a. Data collection

Data collection is the stage where the researcher collects as much data as possible without the limitation of the focus of the research, the data that is collected in large numbers will make research develop and there may be a change in the focus of the research.

b. Data condensation

Data condensation is the process of selecting, focusing, simplifying, abstraction, and the process of transforming data that is close to all parts of written field notes, interview transcripts, documents and empirical materials.

c. Data display

Data presentation is a structured collection of information that provides the possibility of drawing conclusions and taking action. Presentation of data in this study is to present the results of observations, interviews, and analyzed documentation in the form of CW (interview notes), CL (field notes) and CD (documentation notes). The data that has been presented are coded to organize the data, so that researchers can analyze it quickly and easily. The researcher made a preliminary list of codes in accordance with the interview, observation and documentation guidelines.

d. Conclusions; drawing/verifying

Verification is the drawing of conclusions, which means that the activity of the configuration is complete so that later it can answer research questions and research objectives. In this study, researchers made conclusions from the data that had been presented by focusing the discussion and referring to the problem formulation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. HR planning

HR planning is the initial activity of the human resource management process. HR Management is a series of processes carried out by an organization from the planning, development, and evaluation stages to members of the organization to be able to utilize their abilities and contribute to the effectiveness of an organization for achieving its goals. Sutrisno [5] adds regarding the scope of the field of human resource management, the first is human resource planning which includes planning the quality and quantity of human resources as well as job design activities for human resources that contain the most job design. The second scope is the acquisition and placement of human resources, this second field includes recruitment, selection and placement. The next scope of HR management is human resource development, this third area includes career development (assignments) and development of their work abilities. The same thing also expressed by Omebe [13] who conducted research on HR with results that showed that human resources are the key to accelerating socio-economic development and efficient service delivery. That is why this research emphasizes that without an adequate, skilled, and motivated workforce, then the development resource

management program might not be done well. Every education system at every level is very dependent on human resources for the implementation of the program.

HR management in schools begins with planning. Planning is the beginning of the preparation of school needs regarding the number of employees needed. To realize HR management activities need to be supported by HR planning activities where the determination of planning activities is contained in the process of recruitment, selection, HR development, compensation, performance appraisal, and placement as well as assignments. The same thing was revealed by Olaleye [14] in her research with the result that recruitment must be advertised in the media and the internet. The selection must be done transparently, new teachers recruited are guided by experienced teachers and there is a training program. Programs must be arranged so that teachers can improve better performance. HR planning is also seen in the following three schools they are, SDIT Annida Sokaraja, SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto and SD Terpadu Putra Harapan they are carry out the recruitment of teaching staff at the beginning of the academic year. In creating employee vacancies, all three schools use printed and electronic social media via the internet or whatsapp messages. The job advertisement displayed various kinds of requirements and formations needed by the school, as well as the schedule for the selection that began with the collection of administrative documents. Different from the two other schools, SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto all the series of recruitment of employees are from the recruitment, selection, to placement of employees who run are the LPP (Education and Teaching Institute) and the announcement of employee vacancies is available on the Al Irsyad website. So for prospective employees must be active in opening the website to find out information about employee vacancies.

Recruitment is the initial process to look for employees that suitable for the needs of the school and the desired requirements to help the school achieve its goals and make the school superior and quality. Therefore, in selecting the three schools it is very selective starting from the recruitment process then selection and finally placement in order to get potential teaching staff and in accordance with the needs of the school. It was also revealed by Rebore [15] through the human resource planning process, a school district ensured that it had the right number of people, with the right skills, in the right place, and the right time and that people this can effectively carry out tasks that will assist the organization in achieving its goals. In addition Gorton in Bafadal [16] added "the active pursuit of potential candidates for the purpose of influencing them to apply for position in the school district". The definition shows that recruitment is an active process to get prospective educators and educational staff who are very potential to carry out tasks in school.

The next step after recruitment is selection. SDIT Annida Sokaraja, SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto and SD Terpadu Putra Harapan carried out the recruitment of educators at the beginning of the academic year and then each prospective educator collected administrative files as the beginning of the selection stage. Selection is a series through which employees make decisions. Handoko [17] explains that what is meant by "the selection process is a series of activity steps used to decide whether an applicant is accepted or not." These steps include integrating the applicant's and agency's job needs. In the selection there are also various kinds of devices or tests passed as explained by Rebore [15] that the selection process is carried out through a series of steps namely: 1) Write a job description; 2) Set the selection criteria; 3) Write a job vacancy announcement and placing ad; 4) Accept employee candidate in an application; 5) Select employee candidate to be interviewed; 6) Interview the employee candidate; 7) Check credentials and references; 8) Choose the best candidate; 9) Apply for job offers and acceptance; 10) Tell unsucceeded candidates.

Sunaengsih [18] explained that there were three stages in the selection process. First, there was pre-selection which involved policies and the selection procedure; second selection is submission of selection and implementation of rules; the third post-selection, namely the list of applicants' abilities, personnel, contract making, and employee placement. The stages of selection were also carried out by the three SDIT Annida Sokaraja, SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto and SD Terpadu Putra Harapan, after completing the paperwork administration step, they will be called back and contacted by the foundation to take the next stage of the test; there are written tests, religious tests, interview tests, health tests, psychological tests, and microteaching tests. All stages will be passed by each prospective educator until the final stage, namely the delivery of results and acceptance. After the announcement is received, the next step is work placement.

Rohman [19] revealed that the purpose of recruitment, selection, and placement is to match individual characteristics (such as knowledge, skills, and experience) with the job requirements that the individual must have in holding a position. The next stage after selection is employee recruitment and work placement. Prospective employees who are accepted will be announced on the school website or contacted directly by the school which will then be placed according to available vacancies. The placement factor of the teaching staff looks at the needs of the school and also the skills and abilities of each individual. Danumiharja [20] explained that orientation, placement, and assignment are activities that are carried out simultaneously.

Orientation to accelerate education and education personnel and acceptance of the work environment so that teaching and education personnel can immediately adapt to systems, procedures and work culture. Placement and assignment is a decision to educators and education staff based on "the right man on the right job".

The factors that are taken into consideration in the placement of employees include education; work knowledge; work skills be it mental, physical and social skills; and work experience. Furthermore, Arifin [6] explains that there are three types of placements, namely promotion, which occurs when an employee is transferred from one job to another; furthermore there is a transfer, which occurs when an employee is transferred from one position to another whose payment, responsibility and position are the same or relatively the same; Finally, there is a demotion, which occurs when an employee is demoted from a higher position to another lower position.

The placement of educators by the three SDIT Annida Sokaraja, SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto and SD Terpadu Putra Harapan in accordance with the needs of the school and also looking at the abilities and expertise of each individual. The placement of educators was also seen from their ability when conducting the selection test. During selection, the assessment team paid attention to the skills and abilities they display, which is what they consider when they will be placed in a certain position, so that the school places people according to their skills and abilities. Placement must be based on job descriptions and predetermined job specifications, as submitted Elbadiansyah [21] explains that there are two important elements in job analysis, namely the Job Description and Job Specification elements. Job Description is a systematic record of duties and responsibilities in a particular position, while Job Specification is a list of knowledge, skills, abilities, and other characteristics that individuals must possess to carry out a job.

The stages after employee placement are induction, orientation, or introduction of new workplace programs. The aim is that new employees can adapt quickly to the new workplace environment with new people, jobs and also a new work culture. Rebore [15] added that induction is a process designed to introduce newly employed individuals to the school system and with other staff members. It is also a process for introducing reassigned employees to their new school, program, and coworkers. Induction programs at the three SDIT Annida Sokaraja, SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto and SD Terpadu Putra Harapan were well implemented. The induction program is carried out between 30-40 days at school. Unlike the two other schools, SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto held an induction for 30 days and stayed overnight. For one month, prospective employees of Al Irsyad during the job training period will stay overnight and be monitored by an assessment team from the LPP. For two other schools SDIT Annida Sokaraja and SD Terpadu Putra Harapan, the induction program is guidance from the foundation, curriculum, students, and guidance from senior teachers.

Thus it can be concluded that HR planning activities start from the preparation of needs, recruitment, selection, placement, and then orientation and adaptation of new workplaces. The difference is found in the SD IT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto compared to other elementary schools, that in the recruitment of new employees at all levels is run by the LPP both from recruitment to orientation. Each selection phase will be announced on the website and there is a job orientation period for new employees staying for a month.

3.2. HR development

In schools, educators are the main resource in the implementation of education in schools. In order to improve the quality of education in a school, the existing resources, namely teachers must be able to develop their professionalism as a support in developing themselves and their duties. The development of human resources can be through education and training. This was revealed by Sutrisno [5] that development is seen as improving the quality of human resources through training and education programs with the aim of improving the quality of professionalism and skills of employees in carrying out their duties and functions optimally. Research conducted by Ojebiyi and Amos [22] showed that so that a quality education system can be achieved, the Government through various Education Management sectors needs to sponsor its staff for service training, workshops, conferences, seminars, etc. for optimal service delivery in various ways. Based on that, HR development was also carried out by the three SDIT Annida Sokaraja, SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto and SD Terpadu Putra Harapan both through education and training. SDIT Annida conducted routine training once every two weeks every Saturday. While SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto the training participated by the staff was scheduled by the LPP. Then for the SD Terpadu Putra Harapan the training that followed was in the form of seminars and workshops which mostly involved inclusive education.

HR development through training is one of the programs initiated by schools to develop and improve the quality of employees in schools. As stated by Cascio [23] that training consists of planned programs designed to improve performance at the individual, group, and/or organizational level. Training

conducted by educators can be in schools in the form of training or internal school seminars that invite external speakers or conducted outside the workplace to attend workshops or seminars that support work.

Sutrisno [5] revealed that training helps employees understand practical knowledge and its application in order to improve the skills, skills, and attitudes needed by organizations in an effort to achieve goals, while education is an activity to improve theoretical mastery and skills to decide on issues which concerns activities to achieve goals. The training needs are grouped into three parts according to Riniwati [24] namely the need to meet demands; the need to meet the demands of other positions; and the need to meet the demands of change. Nugroho [25] argued that "a systematically structured training should utilize appropriate methods to increase learning motivation, reduce boredom levels until finally the participants can show their best achievements".

Apart from training, there is also the development of human resources through education. Further education can be done by educators to support their performance in school. The three schools, SDIT Annida Sokaraja, SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto and SD Terpadu Putra Harapan, if the teaching staff wishes to continue their studies it will be permitted from their workplace but for SDIT Annida Sokaraja and SD Terpadu Putra Harapan has not provided further study scholarships for employees who want to go to school again. Unlike the two schools, SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto provides further study scholarships on condition that they have served in the workplace for ten years.

HR development can be done education and training. In addition, there are also career development for employees. Career in question is a position or position carried by an employee in his workplace. This was revealed by Cascio [23] who stated that a career is a sequence of positions occupied by someone for life. The carrier in these schools could be seen from the position of teacher to the office of the principal. SDIT Annida Sokaraja and SD Terpadu Putra Harapan, the initial position of the teacher, the accompanying teacher, after that became the homeroom teacher. Teachers could get the chance to become a headmaster if they got a promotion from the foundation, then selected the school principal every four years. Unlike the two schools, SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto began with the class teacher, then the headmaster, after that continues to become the school principal. Same as the two other schools, the principal's position began with the promotion of the foundation, and then who meets the requirements will undergo a test to be the principal. But the difference with the two other schools is that if at SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto, positions can return to their initial positions, for example, they had become school principals, then one day they could be teachers again.

3.3. HR assessment

The assessment of teaching staff in schools takes the form of supervision conducted by the school principal. Work assessment in the form of supervision is held as feedback related to ability, fatigue, shortcomings, and potential, which in turn is useful to determine goals, paths, plans, and career development. The same thing was expressed by Ratnasari [26] work performance is the appearance of the work of human resources in an organization. while work performance appraisal is an evaluation of work performance. Elbadiansyah [21] stated the same thing that performance appraisal also means activities to obtain information that is useful in making decisions related to other human resource management activities such as planning, career development, programs, and employee dismissal.

Supervision process that had been done in three schools started from created a schedule for the supervision of school principals, then prepared learning tools, learning administration, media, and teaching aids that will be used when supervision takes place. The headmaster enters the class that will be supervised according to a predetermined schedule, then while in class the headmaster recorded both the shortcomings and potential of the teacher to be delivered immediately after supervision so that the performance in the next supervision is better. Elbadiansyah [21] explains that the first performance appraisal process is job analysis, namely identifying a position or position in a job. Furthermore, the determination of performance standards is used to compare the work results of employees with predetermined standards. then the work appraisal system, namely there are four systems, namely performance appraisal based on behavior; performance appraisal based on individual employee characteristics and traits, work appraisal based on work results and combined work appraisal based on several elements such as characteristics, characteristics, behavior, and individual employee work results.

Employee performance appraisal in SDIT Annida Sokaraja, SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto and SD Terpadu Putra Harapan routinely carried out every semester by the headmaster with the aim of measuring work performance. As for the other objectives conveyed by Ratnasari, [26] that the purpose of holding performance appraisal, including:

- a. Administrative, which provides directions for promotion, transfer, and salary increases.
- b. Informative, namely providing data to management about the work performance of subordinates and providing data to individuals about their strengths and weaknesses.

- c. Motivation, namely creating learning experiences to motivate staff to develop themselves and improve their work performance.

Besides being supervised by the principal, there are also other assessments for the teaching staff at the school. SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto, besides routine supervision from the school principal, there are also assessments of Quran memorization and daily practices. While SD Terpadu Putra Harapan besides supervision from the headmaster there is also a memorization of the 30 Al Qur'an and an attendance assessment.

3.4. HR compensation system

Compensation is a reward received by an employee for compensation during work in the form of material or non-material. The same thing was explained by Handoko [17] "Compensation is everything that employees or officials receive in return for their work which is important for employees as individuals, because the amount of compensation reflects the measure of the value of their work among the employees themselves, their families and the community". In addition Rebore [15] explained five variables that must be considered in the compensation program, namely: employee performance, effort, seniority, skills, and work requirements. The compensation received by the employees of the three SDIT Annida Sokaraja, SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto and SD Terpadu Putra Harapan were varies depending on the type of employee position.

There are several types of employees, namely contract employees, foundation temporary employees, and permanent foundation employees. All the same, get a basic salary, the difference is the benefits received by employees. The benefits were also based on years of service and employee service. Besides the basic salary and benefits, there were also rewards given by the school or foundation because of employee performance. Providing compensation to employees can increase work motivation because if there is an increase in compensation and welfare received, humanly it has an impact on employee performance motivation. This is according to what Cascio [23] revealed that compensation which includes direct cash payments, indirect payments in the form of employee benefits, and incentives is a supporting factor to motivate employees in order to improve work productivity and strengthen work relations between employees.

4. CONCLUSION

The results showed that: HR planning includes forming the preparation of school HR needs, employee recruitment begins with the opening of vacancies along with the required requirements. After recruitment, there is a selection test to recruit prospective employees and if they have been selected enter the placement stage according to their respective job descriptions and experience the new workplace, the orientation period. At the Al Irsyad School from the KB level through high school, all who take care of prospective employees from recruitment to placement are Education and Teaching Steps (LPP).

HR development includes education and training. Training is carried out through a variety of workshops, seminars, or coaching conducted both internally or outside school. Then for education, employees were needed to continue their studies to a higher level either Bachelor, Master, or Doctor. At SDIT Annida Sokaraja and SD Terpadu Putra Harapan had not provided further study scholarship programs, so if you wish to continue schooling then you will use an independent fee. In contrast to SD IT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto which provided advanced study scholarships for both Bachelor, Master, and Doctor with the requirement to serve for ten years at the Al Irsyad foundation. Other development is through career. Teachers can rise to the position of Principal if they get a promotion from the foundation of each school and meet the required requirements.

HR assessment is conducted by the Headmaster which was routinely carried out every semester. The principal assessed teachers in the form of classroom supervision by assessing teacher performance in teaching and learning administration. Another assessment was also carried out by SDIT Al Irsyad Al Islamiyyah 2 Purwokerto, besides school supervision, there was also an Al Qur'an memorization review and daily practice. The same thing happened in the SD Terpadu Putra Harapan, not only from the supervision assessment, but the presence of employee attendance and memorization juz 30 Al Quran became an additional value for employees in Putra Harapan.

The HR compensation system was given to all employees in the school according to the type and position of the employee. Starting with contract employees, temporary foundation employees, and permanent foundation employees. Besides the basic salary, of course, there were other benefits provided based on the SOP of each school. The length of service and performance of employees is affected by the compensation they receive. Associated with compensation and welfare provided by the school, of course, very influential on employee motivation at work. If there is an enhancement, the motivation to work will increase.

REFERENCES

- [1] DPR dan Presiden Republik Indonesia, *National education system (in Bahasa)*. Jakarta Direktorat Pendidik. Menengah Umum, 2003,
- [2] PMP Nasional, R Indonesia, *Inclusive education for students with disabilities and potential intelligence and/or special talents (in Bahasa)*. Jakarta: Depdiknas, 2009
- [3] M. T. Ilahi, *Inclusive education: Concept and application (in Bahasa)*. Yogyakarta: Ar-Ruzz Media, 2013.
- [4] S. Arikunto and L. Yuliana, *Educational management (in Bahasa)*. Yogyakarta: Graha Cendekia, 2016.
- [5] E. Sutrisno, *Human resourch management (in Bahasa), 8th ed.* Jakarta: Kencana, 2016.
- [6] N. Arifin, *Human resourch management: Theory and case (in Bahasa)*. UNISNU PRESS, 2013.
- [7] Nandini and H. Taj, "Inclusive education: Key role of teachers for its success," *Int. J. Inf. Futur. Res.*, vol. 1, no. 9, pp. 201-208, 2014.
- [8] R. B. Okongo, G. Ngao, N. K. Rop, and W. J. Nyongesa, "Effect of availability of teaching and learning resources on the implementation of inclusive education in pre-school centers in Nyamira North Sub-County, Nyamira County, Kenya," *J. Educ. Pract.*, vol. 6, no. 35, pp. 132-141, 2015,
- [9] Z. M. Jelas, "Learner diversity and inclusive education: A new paradigm for teacher education in Malaysia," *Procedia - Soc. Behav. Sci.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 201-204, 2010.
- [10] D. Csorba, "Design and delivery of a training program for teachers in primary education: Interdisciplinary organization for the key competences training for young school children, from pre-school class to class IV," *Procedia - Soc. Behav. Sci.*, vol. 76, pp. 285-290, 2013.
- [11] M. Hamid, S. Maheen, A. Cheem, and R. Yaseen, "Impact of human resource management on organizational performance," *J. Account. Mark.*, vol. 06, no. 01, pp. 100-116, 2017
- [12] M. B. Miles, A. M. Huberman, and J. Saldana, *Qualitative data analysis: A methods sourcebook, 3rd ed.* USA: SAGE Publications, 2014.
- [13] C. A. Omebe, "Human resource management in education: Issues and challenges," *Br. J. Educ.*, vol. 2, no. 7, pp. 26-31, 2014.
- [14] F. O. Olaleye, "Improving teacher performance competency through effective human resource practices in Ekiti State Secondary Schools," *Singaporean J. Bus. , Econ. Manag. Stud.*, vol. 1, no. 11, pp. 125-132, 2013.
- [15] R. W. Rebore, *Human resource administration in education: A management approach, 9th ed.* USA: Pearson Education Inc, 2011.
- [16] I. Bafadal, *Increasing elementary school profesionalism (in Bahasa)*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara, 2003.
- [17] T. H. Handoko, *Presonal management and human resource, 2nd ed (in Bahasa)*. Yogyakarta: BPFY Yogyakarta, 2001.
- [18] C. Sunaengsih, *Education management textbook (in Bahasa), 1st ed.* Sumedang: UPI Sumedang Press, 2017.
- [19] A. Rohman, *Textbook of human resource management (reinforcing Islamic values in an organization) (in Bahasa)*. Pamekasan: Duta Media Publishing, 2017.
- [20] M. Danumiharja, *A teaching profesion (in Bahasa), 1st ed.* Yogyakarta: Deepublish, 2017.
- [21] Elbadiansyah, *Human resource management (in Bahasa)*. Malang: CV IRDH, 2019.
- [22] O. A. Ojebiyi and A. A. Amos, "Quality human resources management for effective educational system," *Glob. J. Manag. Bus. Res. Adm. Manag.*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 1-8, 2013.
- [23] W. F. Cascio, *Managing human resource: Productivity, quality of work life, profits., 9th ed.* Newyork: The McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc, 2013.
- [24] H. Riniwati, *Human resource management (Main activity and human resource development) (in Bahasa), 1st ed.* Malang: UB Press, 2016.
- [25] Y. A. B. Nugroho, *Training and developing human resource theory and application (in Bahasa)*. Jakarta: Universitas Katolik Indonesia Atma Jaya, 2019.
- [26] S. L. Ratnasari, *(Human capital) human resource management (in Bahasa), 1st ed.* Pasuruan: CV. Penerbit Qiara Media, 2019.

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